

Investigating the Motive Reasons of Blood Donation in Blood Banks of Babylon Province

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Introduction:

Blood is described as a connective tissue. It provides one of the means of communication between the cells of different parts of the body and it is composed of a fluid part called plasma and a cellular mass called Corpuscles. Blood transfusion is an essential component of the health care system of every country and patients who require blood transfusion service as part of the clinical management of their condition have the right to expect that sufficient and safe blood will be available to meet their needs. One blood donation (1 pint) can save up to three lives. Blood is made up of three different life saving components which include plasma, platelets, and red blood cells. Blood cannot be manufactured; it can only come from generous donors (1).

Transfusion of blood and its related products is still one of the major medical interventions utilized in treatment of serious conditions such as trauma, surgery and chemotherapy. There is almost always an urgent need for blood to save a life; therefore, it is imperative that hospitals and urgent clinics always have immediate access to a certain amount of blood and its related products. Blood transfusion, the gift of blood constitutes an important part in overall supply chain. The aforementioned underscores the importance of recruitment of safe blood donors. To ensure the best clinical outcomes, appropriate and safe blood and blood products should be collected and readily available to be used in special medical conditions (2).

Despite significant progress in the field of clinical sciences, recruitment of safe blood donors and maintaining a sufficient supply of safe blood remains a challenge. The best and safest method of blood donation is voluntary non-remunerated donation. Voluntary blood donation is practiced more in countries with higher income. It has been reported that the rate of blood donation in developed countries is 18 times higher than in developing countries (3).

Each year the demand for blood rises five to seven percent without a similar increase in blood donations. Reasons for this demand are associated with an aging population,

increasingly complex surgeries, aggressive chemotherapy regimens, and a decline of eligible donors. The increased requirement for blood transfusion make a challenge for blood transfusion centers to balance between the number of blood donations and demand for blood transfusion (4).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), out of 118.2 million global blood collections, about 60% is collected in developing countries [15]. WHO further reports that there is an obvious difference in the blood donation rate between different countries. The median blood donation ratio in high-income countries is 31.5 donations per 1,000 individuals while it is 15.9, 6.8, and 5.0 in upper-middle-income, lower-middle-income, and low-income countries, respectively. Also, at least 13 million donors were deferred owing to the presence of transfusion-transmitted infection (TTI). Due to this, blood donor recruitment and selection forms the basis of blood transfusion safety, intended to maintain the health of both donors and recipients. The WHO recommends the collection of blood from voluntary, non-remunerated blood donors (VERBS) belonging to low-risk groups (5). World Health Organization reports reveal that in a developing country more than 50 percent of blood donations are made by paid donors (6).

Generally, donors are classified into the following categories: voluntary, family replacement, remunerated or paid donors, and autologous donor (7). There are replacement donors who donate blood for their friends, relatives to compensate for using the available blood. Conversely, ignorance, fear and misconceptions about blood donations and lack of voluntary blood donation camps are considered to be the major factors impeding blood donation activity in developing countries vis-à-vis western counterparts (8).

This study try to assert if the people participate in voluntary blood donation because volunteering brings certain purposes to them or because they might have different underlying beliefs, purposes, or perceived functions. In a try to build up a framework for blood donation intentions as it will provide insights into predicting behavior and maneuvering strategy to retain potential donors for future donation as the commercial donors were usually lower, in terms of blood safety.

Aim of study

Assessment the motives for voluntary blood donation in the donors of Babylon blood bank.

Materials and Methods

A cross sectional observational study was conducted in between November 2020 to February 2021 recruiting 300 volunteers blood donors from Babylon Central Blood Bank in Al-Hilla city the center of Babylon province. A questionnaire was developed consisting of few questions related to the intention of blood donation in addition to gender and age.

Results and Discussion

The 300 participants have a mean age of 33.7 ± 6.2 years with a range of 20 to 55 years. The age groups divided in to three categories according to figure (1). The higher frequency belong to the age group of (20-30) years as this group represent the youth part of society who were the electants for most replacement donation. The second group (31.3%) was the (31-40) years group who are the age group having erythrocytosis mostly as it was little to see some one of this age group who were not smoker. The lowest frequency of the donors were those who are > 41years old (22%) as this group rarely presented without chronic disease so they are less electant for blood donation.

Figure (1): Distribution of age groups among the blood donors

Female donors represent only **8.3%** of the total as awareness regarding blood donation is higher among females, fear from the process, and cultural taboos which prefer female to remain indoors. In addition to temporary deferral conditions like low haemoglobin values, low weight which is quite understandable since women within the donor age range usually may have one factor or another interfering with their chances of

being suitable to donate. Factors such as their frequent menstrual cycles, pregnancy, and lactation may prevent them from donation. This study represent higher female gender participation in blood donation than a study accomplished in Mosul city, Nineveh governorate, Iraq where the percent of female donors was 0.57 % only (9). Also this finding agreed but with higher frequency with the results of R Majumder in India where only 3.6% of the donors were female (10).

The sample chosen for this study divided in to three groups according to the motive of blood donation. Group-1 (149) 49.6% donate blood voluntary to alleviate high Hb status resulted from erythrocytosis, group-2 (137) 45.6% donate blood involuntary (replacement) as a need for a relative patient , and group-3 (14) 4.6% donate blood voluntary for humanity motives (autologous donors) as in figure (2). Remunerated or paid donors didn't present in current study.

Figure (2): Distribution of blood donation motives

From the results in figure (2); About half of the blood donors were give their blood to alleviate erythrocytosis presented as Hb value of ≥ 16.5 g/dL and PCV of ≥ 49 %. Polycythemia or erythrocytosis is an increase in RBCs, packed cell volume (PCV), hemoglobin (Hb) concentration. It could be primary erythropoietin (EPO) independent or secondary EPO dependent. Secondary polycythemia is the one which we can manipulate, it mostly caused by smoking (11). according to the WHO criteria to diagnose polycythemia; (male with Hb value of ≥ 16.5 g/dL and PCV of ≥ 49 %, and female with Hb value of ≥ 16.0 g/dL and PCV of ≥ 48 %, are

considered as having a case of polycythemia). Their donation was therapeutic (11). The high no. of males with erythrocytosis in Iraqi population may be due to the prevalence of cigarette smoking among Iraqi males as reported by Economics of Tobacco for the Middle East and North Africa (MNA) Region who stated that the prevalence of smoking among the young people in Iraq is 23% (12). Al-Omary H. et al reviewed that tobacco use in the Middle East is reported to be the highest rate of smoking internationally with smoking rates from 40% to 60% for cigarettes and reaching rates of 77% for men and 35% in women, in some Arab countries (13). This result agreed with Roy A. et al who reported that cigarette smokers are known to have higher concentrations of hemoglobin who represent high ratio of blood donors (14). A study in Nineva reported that the prevalence of polycythemic subjects among total blood donors in Mosul city is 1.65 %, which is much lower than that noticed in current study (9).

The low ratio about 5% of voluntary blood donation for humanity motives to save lives in spite of the religious nature of Al-Hilla population which agreed that blood donation is a religious process may be due to several factors. One of the causes is the lack of time; so providing mobile teams may resolve the issue. Some donors felt that the fear of pain is the main cause of reluctance from blood donation as concluded by Al-Nuri et al in Al-Mousil city (9). This result bring a necessity for more researches to learn what “captures” donors and how to improve the psychological commitment to continue to donate blood.

The causes stand behind involuntary (replacement) donation as this motive represent 45% of donation were categorized as: chronic disease, anemia, accidents by cars, work or terrorism, the need for surgery procedures, and finally the donation for COVID-19 patient; all are expressed in figure (2).

Figure (2): Frequent causes behind replacement blood donation

The main cause is the chronic non-communicable diseases (hypertension, diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disease, stroke, asthma and epilepsy) which is highly prevalent in Iraqi population as a result of subsequent stressful conditions like wars, terrorism, economic blockade, forced displacement, poverty, and unstable political conditions and other armed conflicts along fifty years (15). In addition to bad life habits resulted from ignorance, destruction of the health system infrastructures, lack of food and safe water, poor sanitation, lack of medical care and health services all associated with high rate of chronic diseases in Iraqi population represent a need for frequent blood administration to them (15).

Anemia is present in different types in Iraqi population; iron deficiency anemia, thalassemia. The prevalence of anemia among adolescents was 12.9 and 17.6% in rural and urban regions in Iraq respectively as reported by Al-Attar Z et al (16).

Blood administration for victims of accidents and terrorism appeared to be 21% as in figure (2) which consume the blood banks stock in spite of replacement donation by the relatives as the replacement donation may not meet the need to resuscitate the injured victims.

Surgical procedures and corona patients depends on the replacement donation mainly; so it does not exhaust the blood bank stock.

Conclusion

The main motive of blood donation was found to be therapeutic donation for treatment of erythrocytosis.

Recommendations

- Regarding replacement donors; improving the quality of blood bank services to increase the intention to come back in the upcoming months for voluntary donation.
- Encouragement and improving of commitment, educational programs to avoid negative motivation, like fear of needle or sight of blood or pin prick, medical excuse.
- Regarding female blood donors small incentives like certificates, providing transport of blood donors may make a difference in increasing no. of female participation.

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